

Use of Satire, Music, and Comedy for Sharing COVID-19 Information on Social Media by Nigeria Undergraduates

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Purpose: Dynamism in information sharing has emerged over time since the advent of advanced means of mass communication. Social media and their creative use have been playing significant roles in facilitating the processes of social interaction through which vital life sustaining information are shared. Adopting the Use and Gratification theory, this study was designed to investigate the practice and motivators of Nigeria undergraduates' use of satire, music, and comedy for sharing COVID-19 information on social media.

Research questions:

1. Through what medium do Nigeria undergraduates receive most information on COVID-19?
2. What are the social media platforms used mostly by Nigeria undergraduates for sharing COVID-19 information?
3. What motivates Nigeria undergraduates' choice of using a specific social media platform for sharing COVID-19 information?
4. To what extent do Nigeria undergraduates share COVID-19 information on social media?
5. To what extent do Nigeria undergraduates use satire, music and comedy for information sharing on COVID-19?
6. Among satire, music and comedy, which is the most used by Nigeria undergraduates for the sharing of COVID-19 information and what motivates them?

Methodology: By convenience sampling, 294 undergraduates from six federal universities in Southwest, Nigeria participated in the survey. The majority, 132(44.9%) were from the University of Lagos (UNILAG), 69(23.5%) were from Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta (FUNAAB),

34(11.6%) were from University of Ibadan, Ibadan (UI), 26(8.8%) were from Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife (OAU), 23(7.8%) were from Federal University of Technology Akure (FUTA), while just 10(3.4%) were from the Federal University Oye Ekiti (FUOYE). A questionnaire was posted on online platforms to collect data from the participants. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics with tables and charts adopted in the presentation of results.

Findings: Findings revealed that the undergraduates received most information on COVID-19 on social media. This is contrary to the findings of Ali et al (2020) and Hamzat and Otulugbu (2020), but it is in consonance with the findings of Umeizudike et al (2020); Adebowale et al (2021) whose studies, carried out among Nigeria undergraduates revealed that most information on COVID-19 were received on social media. Further findings revealed that the most used of the social media platforms for sharing COVID-19 information was WhatsApp (82.7%). This is in line with the findings of Sulaiman et al (2020); Mbodila et al (2020); and Hamzat and Otulugbu (2020) that WhatsApp was the most used for sharing COVID-19 information. Satire ($\bar{x}=2.52$), music ($\bar{x}=2.51$), and comedy ($\bar{x}=3.14$) were moderately used with comedy (48.2%) used mostly. While some of the undergraduates added satirical comments, music, or comedy (e.g. satirical statements, comic gif, cartoons, music clips or songs) to share COVID-19 information; for example some indicated they created cartoon on coronavirus infection ($\bar{x} = 2.12$, $SD = 0.903$), they composed songs on coronavirus infection, which they shared with their friends ($\bar{x} = 2.12$, $SD = 0.961$) others indicated that the information they received or shared were already in the form of satire, music or comedy. For example they received some humorous stories on corona virus infection from their colleagues ($\bar{x}=3.43$, $SD = 1.021$), some of the information on corona virus pandemic they received were in form of cartoon ($\bar{x}=3.06$, $SD = 1.066$), shared music on coronavirus infection as received ($\bar{x}=2.52$, $SD = 1.187$), received comedies on coronavirus infection from their friends and family members ($\bar{x}=3.24$, $SD = 1.058$) among others. Similarly, the studies done by Cabedo-Mas et al (2021); Glăveanu and de Saint Laurent (2021); Karmegam and Mapillairaju (2020); Ogembo et al (2021); Onuora et al (2021); and Thompson et al (2021) also confirmed that people used satire, music and comedy to share COVID-19 information on social media. Self-recognition, comfortability, promotion of creativity, fun and enjoyment, entertainment, emotional support, and provision of escape from fear associated with the news of coronavirus pandemic were among the motivators for the use of comedy for sharing COVID 19 information on social media.

Contribution: This paper contributes to the body of knowledge in several ways. First, it makes the contribution for academics and practitioners to understand that the uses and gratifications theory applies not only to the use of social media and other mass communication media, but also to the use of media contents such as satire, music and comedy which are equally media of communication. Secondly, it has contributed to existing literature by demonstrating that satire, music and comedy can be used to share vital health information even in time of emergencies. It is in this connection that it is recommended that public health stakeholders in Nigeria should incorporate the use of these media contents which are emotion friendly to share credible health information in time of public health emergencies, now and in the future.

Research limitations: This present study has limitations in terms of the use of only quantitative method and a limited sample size of 294 participants from only six federal universities in southwest Nigeria which makes generalizability impossible. The small size of the sample was not unconnected with the fact that the study was conducted during the peak period of the onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic when many Nigerians were ambivalent and apathetic about goings on around them. A larger sample and a mixed method approach are therefore suggested to enable a deeper probing of the topic and provide a basis for generalisation of the findings. Further studies could also look into the effects of demographic characteristics on the use of satire, music and comedy for sharing COVID-19 information.

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